

Publishing data?! How do you do that then?

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and many others, including members of the PREPARDE and NERC data citation and publication project teams and the CODATA working group on data citation

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Tuesday Tutorial @Ten 21st May 2013

Who are we and why do we care about data?

The UK's Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) funds six data centres which between them have responsibility for the long-term management of NERC's environmental data holdings.

We deal with a variety of environmental measurements, along with the results of model simulations in:

- Atmospheric science
- Earth sciences
- Earth observation
- Marine Science
- Polar Science
- Terrestrial & freshwater science, Hydrology and Bioinformatics

Even the Chancellor says data's important!

“The next generation of scientific discovery will be data-driven discovery.....”

“We need to make sure we capture value from this mass of data – both for economic growth and for social advances, such as better health.”

“This requires a transformation in data management”

Speech by the Chancellor of the Exchequer,
Rt Hon George Osborne MP, to the Royal
Society – 9 Nov 2012

Thanks to Jonathan Tedds (University of Leicester)

The Scientific Method

A key part of the scientific method is that it should be reproducible – other people doing the same experiments in the same way should get the same results.

Unfortunately observational data is not reproducible (unless you have a time machine!)

The way data is organised and archived is crucial to the reproducibility of science and our ability to test conclusions.

This is often the only part of the process that anyone other than the originating scientist sees.

We want to change this.

<http://www.mrsaverettsclassroom.com/bio2-scientific-method.php>

Journals have always published data...

Suber cells and mimosa leaves. Robert Hooke, *Micrographia*, 1665

[*Observations of Stars in the Spiral Nebula.* H. 1622.

The spiral form of this nebula is very distinctly seen in the Pulkova refractor. Unfortunately in the month of March, the best season for the observation of this object, the sky was constantly cloudy; so that I could only get three nights' observations in the months of April and May, when the twilight did not cease for the whole night. It must be attributed to this unfavourable circumstance that the following list of determinations is not so complete as it probably would have been without the twilight. The observations have been made alternately with powers of 188 and 207.

Observations.

Date.	Object.	Magnitude.	Ang. Pos.	No. of measures.	Distance.	No. of measure.
1851, April 7.	N n	14 55	5	267-1	4
	N a	a = (11)	229 24	3	88-0	3
	N b	b = (11.12)	109 12	3	242-6	3
	a b	93 42	3	298-6	3
April 28.	a b	94 23	3	300-8	4
	N a	228 36	4		
	N b	108 54	4		
	n a	283 42	3		
	n b	153 30	3		
	a d	d = (12.13)	323 51	3		
	N d	277 27	3		
	a e	e = (13)	112 13	3		
	N e	161 56	3		
	N f	f = (12.13)	309 18	3		
	a f	237 31	3		
a g	g = (12.13)	215 17	3	115-5	4	
a h	h = (12.13)	193 29	3			
May 3.	g h	87 5	3		
	N k	k = (13.14)	51 47	3		
	n k	173 29	4		
	b k	317 23	3		
	b l	27 20	4		
	n l	l = (11.12)	83 17	4	335-2	4
	a e	112 56	4		
	N e	161 39	3		
	a m	m = (12.13)	172 43	5		
	N m	190 44	4		
b m	238 50	4			
N a	229 12	4	87-0	3	
N n	14 47	4	264-2		

The Scientific Papers of William Parsons, Third Earl of Rosse 1800-1867

...but datasets have gotten so big, it's not useful to publish them in hard copy anymore

Reasons for citing and publishing data

- **Pressure** from (UK) **government** to make data from publicly funded research available for free.
 - **Scientists** want **attribution** and **credit** for their work
 - **Public** want to know what the scientists are doing
 - Good for the **economy** if new industries can be built on scientific data/research
- Research **fund**ers want reassurance that they're getting **value for money**
 - Relies on peer-review of science publications (well established) and data (starting to be done!)
- Allows the wider **research community** and **industry** to **find and use** datasets, and understand the **quality** of the data
- Extra **incentive** for scientists to submit their data to data centres in appropriate formats and with full metadata

<http://www.evidencebased-management.com/blog/2011/11/04/new-evidence-on-big-bonuses/>

Why should I bother putting my data into a repository?

THE FOUR STAGES OF DATA LOSS

DEALING WITH ACCIDENTAL DELETION OF MONTHS OF HARD-EARNED DATA

"Piled Higher and Deeper" by Jorge Cham
www.phdcomics.com

What it all comes down to:

Composite image from Flickr user [bnilsen](#) and Matt Stempeck (NOI), shared under [Creative Commons license](#)

Encourage and provide **credit** to **researchers** and **institutions** for managing and disseminating their data properly.

Making data available is good for science and good for everyone!

For the record!

Part of the Italsat data archive – on CDs in a shelf in my office

What the processed data set looks like on disk

What the raw data files looked like.

Why not just share the data?

Benefits of sharing:

- Ability to discover and reuse data which has already been collected
- Avoid redundant data collection
- Save time and money
- Provide opportunities for collaboration.

Research funders are keen to encourage data sharing.

For the most part, scientists are happy to share other scientists' data, but...

Knowledge is power!

Data may mean the difference between getting a grant and not.

There is (currently) no universally accepted mechanism for data creators to obtain academic credit for their dataset creation efforts.

Creators (understandably) prefer to hold the data until they have extracted all the possible publication value they can.

This behaviour comes at a cost for the wider scientific community.

But if we publish the data, precedence is established and credit is given!

Knowledge is power! (part 2)

"Piled Higher and Deeper" by Jorge Cham
www.phdcomics.com

How to publish data

- Stick it up on a webpage somewhere
 - Issues with stability, persistence, discoverability...
 - Maintenance of the website
- Put it in the cloud
 - Issues with stability, persistence, discoverability...
- Attach it to a journal paper and store it as supplementary materials
 - Journals not too keen on archiving lots of supplementary data, especially if it's large volume.
- Put it in a disciplinary/institutional repository
- Write a data article about it and publish it in a data journal

By David Fletcher
<http://www.cloudtweaks.com/2011/05/the-lighter-side-of-the-cloud-data-transfer/>

“Publishing” versus “publishing” and “Open” versus “Closed”

Distinction between:

Publishing = publishing after some formal process which adds value for the consumer:

- e.g. PloS ONE type review, or
- EGU journal type public review, or
- More traditional peer review.

and

- provides commitment to persistence

And publishing/serving = making available for consumption (e.g. on the web)

We want to:

Encourage scientists to move away from storing their data on CDs in their locked filing cabinets...

....or on hard disks with no backups....

And get them to put their data in a place where it'll be archived and looked after for the future properly...

...where it can be shared/made available/published for the benefit of other researchers/general public/policy makers

...and the data authors will get proper credit for their work!

Creating a dataset is hard work!

DATA: BY THE NUMBERS

"Piled Higher and Deeper" by Jorge Cham
www.phdcomics.com

But sometimes other
people don't get it.

"Piled Higher and Deeper" by Jorge Cham
www.phdcomics.com

What is a Dataset?

DataCite's definition

(http://www.datacite.org/sites/default/files/Business_Models_Principles_v1.0.pdf):

Dataset: "Recorded information, regardless of the form or medium on which it may be recorded including writings, films, sound recordings, pictorial reproductions, drawings, designs, or other graphic representations, procedural manuals, forms, diagrams, work flow, charts, equipment descriptions, data files, data processing or computer programs (software), statistical records, and other research data." (from the U.S. National Institutes of Health (NIH) Grants Policy Statement via DataCite's Best Practice Guide for Data Citation).

In my opinion a dataset is something that is:

- The result of a defined process
- Scientifically meaningful
- Well-defined (i.e. clear definition of what is in the dataset and what isn't)

How is my scarf like a dataset?

- The raw material it's made from doesn't contain information
- But the act of knitting encodes information into the scarf
- The scarf is the result of a well defined process (knitting) and has a particular method used to create it
- I need to be able to describe it
- I need to be able to find it
- I need to store it properly so it doesn't get lost, or corrupted (i.e. eaten by moths or shredded by mice)
- I might need to recreate it so I need to keep information about it
- I put a lot of time and effort into making it, so I'm very attached to it!

<http://www.flickr.com/photos/nazlicetiner/6448303541/>

http://www.flickr.com/photos/maco_nix/5019885742/

Just like not all scarves are the same, not all datasets are the same!

<http://www.flickr.com/photos/lovefibre/3251690074/>

<http://www.flickr.com/photos/halfbisqued/8084145976/>

<http://www.flickr.com/photos/lucathegalga/2282305884/>

<http://www.flickr.com/photos/ujkakevin/2303531028/>

What do we need to support publishing data?

The **scientific quality** of a dataset has to be evaluated by **peer-review** by scientists with domain knowledge. This peer-review process has already been set up by academic publishers, so it makes sense to collaborate with them for peer-review publishing of data.

Can cite using URLs, but we've realised that people don't trust URLs. We're loading DOIs with more meaning than them simply being a persistent identifier – using them to signify **completeness** and **technical quality** of the dataset.

The **day job** – take in data and metadata supplied by scientists (often on an ongoing basis). Make sure that there is adequate metadata and that the data files are appropriate format. Make it available to other interested parties.

- We already have a working method for linking between publications which is:

- commonly used
- understood by the research community
- used to create metrics to show how much of an impact something has (citation counts)
- applied to digital objects (digital versions of journal articles)

- We can extend citation to other things like:

- data
- code
- multimedia

And the best bit is, researchers don't need to learn a new method of linking – they cite like they normally would!

<http://www.naa.gov.au/records-management/capability-development/keep-the-knowledge/index.aspx>

How we (formally) cite data

We use digital object identifiers (DOIs) as part of our dataset citation because:

- They are actionable, interoperable, persistent links for (digital) objects
- Scientists are already used to citing papers using DOIs (and they trust them)
- Academic journal publishers (e.g. Nature) are starting to require datasets be cited in a stable way, i.e. using DOIs.
- The British Library and DataCite approached us to pilot citing data using DOIs – and we've developed a good working relationship

The screenshot shows the DataCite Metadata Search beta interface. The search bar contains the query 'prefix: 10.5285'. The results page shows 44 documents found in 117ms. The first few results are:

- GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements: Sparsholt site (version 1.0) [doi:10.5285/FF55462E-38A4-4F30-B562-F82FF26305C3]
- United Kingdom Butterfly Monitoring Scheme: Collated Indices 2011 [doi:10.5285/FF55462E-38A4-4F30-B562-F82FF26305C3]
- CTD profiles (depth, pressure, temperature, salinity, potential temperature, density, fluorescence, transmittance, downwelling PAR, dissolved oxygen concentration) binned to 0.5 m and 0.25 m at sites L4 and E1 in the Western English Channel between January 2002 and December 2011 [doi:10.5285/9979E595-A2D2-4C93-A317-9E84888CFCTA]
- ITE Land Classification of Great Britain 1990 [doi:10.5285/A0320E08-FAF5-48E1-9EC9-77A213D2907F]
- ITE Land Classification of Great Britain 1998 [doi:10.5285/971671A6-9884-4D80-E165-21DACE727359]
- ITE Land Classification of Great Britain 2007 [doi:10.5285/971671A6-9884-4D80-E165-21DACE727359]
- Mars Analysis Correction Data Assimilation (MACDA): MGS/ITES v1.0 (version 1.0) [doi:10.5285/78114993-E2B0-4601-8AE5-3551E62AEF2D]
- Land Cover Map 2007 (1km percentage Target Class, GB) [doi:10.5285/0C838FF9D-344D-4169-89CE-69853D3A7A63]
- Land Cover Map 2007 (Vector, GB) [doi:10.5285/1079E91A-ABC1-4371-8482-1C1B6709661F]

What sort of data can we/will we assign a DOI to?

Dataset has to be:

- Stable (i.e. not going to be modified)
- Complete (i.e. not going to be updated)
- Permanent – by assigning a DOI we're committing to make the dataset available for posterity
- Good quality – by assigning a DOI we're giving it our data centre stamp of approval, saying that it's complete and all the metadata is available

When a dataset is cited that means:

- There will be bitwise fixity
- With no additions or deletions of files
- No changes to the directory structure in the dataset "bundle"

A DOI should point to a *html* representation of some record which describes a *data object* – i.e. a landing page.

Upgrades to versions of data formats will result in new editions of datasets.

BAD LANDING PAGES

Viewing GBS 20.7GHz slant x

badc.nerc.ac.uk/view/badc.nerc.ac.uk_ATOM_dep_11902119479621181

BADC - Trac METAFOR | Home Google Mail BBC NEWS | News Fr... Sorcha ní gCeallagh... Other bookmarks

Centre for Environmental Data Archival
SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY FACILITIES COUNCIL
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

Search for in All

GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Chilbolton site

General Info

Title: GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Chilbolton site
Type: Activity
Sub-Type: Deployment
Publication State: Citable
URI: http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/view/badc.nerc.ac.uk_ATOM_dep_11902119479621181

Summary

The GBS (Global Broadcast Service) dataset is a series of radio attenuation measurements made at three sites in the UK: Chilbolton and Sparsholt, both in southern UK, and Dundee in Scotland. The aim of the experiment was to make long term measurements of the signal strength received from a 20.7GHz beacon on the US Department of Defense satellite UFO-9 at multiple sites, in order to determine whether the use of site diversity as a fade mitigation technique would be effective. The dataset spans a period of 3 years, from August 2003 to August 2006 with signal attenuation sampled once per second.

Please cite this dataset as:

Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research, [S. A. Callaghan, J. Waight, C. J. Walden, J. Agnew and S. Ventouras], GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Sparsholt site, [Internet]. British Atmospheric Data Centre, 2003-2005, 1st April 2011, doi:10.5285/639a3714-bc74-46a6-9026-64931f355e07

This dataset is cited in:

S. A. Callaghan, J. Waight, J.L.Agnew, C. J. Walden, C.L.Wrench, S. Ventouras "The GBS dataset: measurements of satellite site diversity at 20.7 GHz in the UK", Geoscience Data Journal, 17 March 2013, DOI: 10.1002/gdj3.2

Author

Name email

Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research, [S. A. Callaghan, J. Waight, C. J. Walden, J. Agnew and S. Ventouras]

Online References

Relation	Title
Apply for access	Apply for to GBS data from Chilbolton
Download	Data directory for GBS data from Chilbolton
Documentation	DOI for dataset 10.5285/639a3714-bc74-46a6-9026-64931f355e07
Documentation	Data article in Geoscience Data Journal doi:10.1002/gdj3.2

Associated Data

Type	Title
Data Production Tool	Chilbolton: GBS receiver
Activity	Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR)
Observation Station	Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR), UK

Dataset catalogue page (and DOI landing page)

Dataset citation

Clickable link to Dataset in the archive

STFC Data home | Science x

https://data.isis.stfc.ac.uk/doi/INVESTIGATION/24079886/

Science & Technology
Facilities Council

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ISIS Data

RB920411.

Investigation title: Responsive polymer brushes grafted from gold nanoparticles: interaction with surfactant.

Creator: *Titmuss,S*
Jia,H

DOI: 10.5286/ISIS.E.24079886

Date of Experiment: Sat May 01 08:45:00 BST 2010

Publisher: STFC ISIS Facility

Data format: RAW/Nexus
Select the data format above to find out more about it.

Data Citation

The recommended format for citing this dataset in a research publication is as:
[author], [date], [title], [publisher], [doi]

For Example:
Titmuss,S. et al; (2010): 920411, STFC ISIS Facility, doi:10.5286/ISIS.E.24079886

Abstract

We will use SANS to characterize dispersions of gold nanoparticles functionalized with poly(dimethyl aminoethyl methacrylate) brushes grafted from 25 nm gold nanoparticle interfaces by surface-initiated ATRP. We will characterize the response of the polymer layers to pH and at low pH, where the polymer is cationically charged, to electrolyte concentration. Our main focus however will be to determine the nature of the surfactant aggregates formed in the brushes at concentrations of surfactant that lead to peaks in the surface tension of the dispersions at pH=3 and 10 and also lead to the formation of multilayer structures in equivalent brushes formed at planar interfaces. We will measure under particle-matching contrast, for dispersions bearing hydrogenous pDMAEMA and particle-matching DMAEMA with particle-matching SDS and hydrogenous SDS respectively.

DOWNLOAD
download the dataset

Data collected on the SANS2D instrument at the ISIS facility

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Dataset citation

What else can be on the end of a DataCite DOI? A project report

Assessment of the Butterfi x

nparc.cisti-icist.nrc-cnrc.gc.ca/npsi/ctrl?action=shwart&index=an&req=20337846&lang=en

National Research Council Canada / Conseil national de recherches Canada

Canada

National Research Council Canada
www.nrc-cnrc.gc.ca

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NRC National Science Library

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Frequently Asked Questions

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DataCite Canada
DOCLINE in Canada
PubMed Central Canada
Gateway to Scientific Data
NRC Employees Proxy Server Login
Completed Access to Information Requests
Proactive Disclosure

NRC Publications Archive

[View deposited version](#)
DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4224/20337846>

Assessment of the Butterfly Door as a Means of Egress

Author(s): Proulx, G.; Higgins, D.
Affiliation: NRC Institute for Research in Construction; National Research Council Canada
Language: English
Type: Report
Series: Internal Report, Institute for Research in Construction, National Research Council Canada
Date: 1997
Description: 44 p.
Report #: IRC-IR-748
Identifier #: 7826
NPArC #: 20337846
Keywords: Human behaviour
Abstract: This research project is a joint study between fire safety researchers at the Institute for Research in Construction of the National Research Council of Canada (NRC) and the Société de transport de la communauté urbaine de Montréal (STCUM). The objective of this project was to collect information on the passengers' use of the Butterfly Door for evacuation. To obtain a complete spectrum of information, it was decided to study the daily use of the Butterfly Door, its use with a large crowd of people and its use during two evacuation drills.

Bookmark and Share:

Export | Get Link

Report a Correction Home

What else can be on the end of a DataCite DOI? Educational exhibits

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying the EPOS™ (Electronic Presentation Online System) website. The URL in the address bar is `posterng.netkey.at/esr/online_viewing/index.php?module=view_postercoverage&task=viewcoverage&doi=10.1594/ecr2012/C-1767`. The page features a red header with the EPOS™ logo and the European Society of Radiology (ESR) logo. Navigation buttons for HOME, HELP, Bookmarks, and LOGIN are visible. A search bar contains the text "Go to: > choose".

The main content area displays the poster details for "C-1767 Biliary tree dilation – and now what?". On the left, a sidebar lists sections: Coverage, Learning objectives, Background, Imaging findings OR Procedure details, Conclusion, Personal Information, and References. The main content includes:

- Poster No.:** C-1767
- Poster Score:** 8
- Type:** Educational Exhibit
- Keywords:** Pathology, Diagnostic procedure, Ultrasound, MR, CT, Biliary Tract / Gallbladder
- Authors:** L. Ferreira, A. B. Ramos, S. Magalhães, M. Certo; Porto/PT
- DOI:** 10.1594/ecr2012/C-1767
- Rate this poster:** Overall userrating: 0.00 stars
- Learning objectives:** - To present a systematic diagnostic approach when biliary tree dilation is found - To review the different causes of biliary tree dilation [read more](#)
- Background:** Patients with elevation of bilirubin need to be studied. Investigation normally starts with ultrasound. Ultrasound is a non-invasive and fast technique that can confirm if dilation of biliary tree is or not present, and sometimes can establish its cause. Most of the patients will need further work-up either with Computed Tomography (CT), Magnetic Resonance Cholangiopancreatography (MRCP), endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP), and ultrasound endoscopy. [read more](#)
- Imaging findings OR Procedure details:** CT is an important tool to confirm ultrasound findings, such as pancreatic carcinoma, enabling at the same time disease staging. In our Hospital, because of time consuming examination and lower availability, MRCP is used for patients with suspicious diseases from the biliary tree, such as Caroli's disease or cholangiocarcinoma. In the presence of a normal CT examination, and/or unclear MRCP findings, which can happens for example in small ampullary tumour, ERCP is usually the next imaging... [read more](#)
- Conclusion:** Biliary tree dilation is a common clinical challenge. Sometimes a long diagnostic workup is needed to find the cause of the obstruction. [read more](#)

Additional features include "Add bookmark", "Send a comment", "Send a friend", and "Download PDF" buttons. A "Sidebar" section contains a flowchart and two sets of medical images (A and B).

What else can be on the end of a DataCite DOI? Images

UC3 Merritt: Object -- ark: x

https://merritt.cdlib.org/object?group=cdl_uc3_mdcunc&object=ark%3A%2Fb5060%2Fd2qr4v2t

Logout | Contact UC3 | Help
Logged in as Guest

Merritt

Collection home Change collection ▾

Object: [ark:/b5060/d2qr4v2t](https://merritt.cdlib.org/object?group=cdl_uc3_mdcunc&object=ark%3A%2Fb5060%2Fd2qr4v2t)

Merritt > Collection: [UCLA Modular Digital Course in Undergraduate Neuroscience Education](#) > Object: [ark:/b5060/d2qr4v2t](https://merritt.cdlib.org/object?group=cdl_uc3_mdcunc&object=ark%3A%2Fb5060%2Fd2qr4v2t)

Grisham, William; Jones, Heidi B.; Park, Sun Hee. **Rat spinal cord image archive** (2003)

permanent link: <http://n2t.net/ark:/b5060/d2qr4v2t>
primary identifier: [ark:/b5060/d2qr4v2t](https://merritt.cdlib.org/object?group=cdl_uc3_mdcunc&object=ark%3A%2Fb5060%2Fd2qr4v2t)
title: Rat spinal cord image archive
creator: Grisham, William; Jones, Heidi B.; Park, Sun Hee
date: 2003
local id: doi:10.5060/D2QR4V2T
last modified: 2013-02-01 10:57 AM UTC
created: 2013-02-01 10:43 AM UTC
total size (all versions): 233.7 MB
total versions: 2

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Object Lookup

[Go](#)

Search object author, title, date or identifier.

Current Version

Version 2: 2013-02-01 10:57 AM UTC

- 11S-RDLN-1.tif
- 11S-RDLN-2.tif
- 11S-RDLN-3A.tif
- 11S-RDLN-3B.tif

[652 more files](#)

Prior Versions

Version 1: 2013-02-01 10:43 AM UTC

Merritt is a service of the [University of California Curation Center](#) of the [California Digital Library](#)
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[Privacy policy](#) | [Image credits](#)

Recommended formats for dataset citation

- Don't get hung up on it!
- Most of the time the repository should tell you how to cite the dataset on the catalogue page
 - If they don't – ask them!
- DataCite is “discipline-agnostic concerning matters pertaining to academic style sheet requirements.”
http://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-2.2/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v2.2.pdf
- DataCite recommends rather than requires a particular citation format:
 - Creator(PublicationYear): Title. Publisher. Identifier
- If you want to include the two optional properties, Version and ResourceType:
 - Creator(PublicationYear): Title. Version. Publisher. ResourceType. Identifier

DUTY CALLS [HTTP://XKCD.COM/386/](http://xkcd.com/386/)

Foundations and links are in place – now what?

The **scientific quality** of a dataset has to be evaluated by **peer-review** by scientists with domain knowledge. This peer-review process has already been set up by academic publishers, so it makes sense to collaborate with them for peer-review publishing of data.

Can cite using URLs, but we've realised that people don't trust URLs. We're loading DOIs with more meaning than them simply being a persistent identifier – using them to signify **completeness** and **technical quality** of the dataset.

The **day job** – take in data and metadata supplied by scientists (often on an ongoing basis). Make sure that there is adequate metadata and that the data files are appropriate format. Make it available to other interested parties.

Publishing data for the scholarly record

- Scientific journal publication mainly focuses on the **analysis, interpretation and conclusions** drawn from a given dataset.
- Examining the raw data that forms the dataset is more difficult, as datasets are usually stored in digital media, in a variety of (proprietary or non-standard) formats.
- **Peer-review** is generally only applied to the methodology and final conclusions of a piece of work, and **not the underlying data** itself. But if the conclusions are to stand, the **data must be of good quality**.
- A process of **data publication**, involving peer-review of datasets would be of benefit to many sectors of the academic community.

Most scientists regarded the new streamlined peer-review process as 'quite an improvement.'

<http://libguides.luc.edu/content.php?pid=5464&sid=164619>

The traditional online journal model

Overlay journal model for publishing data

What is a data article?

A **data article** describes a **dataset**, giving details of its collection, processing, software, file formats, etc., without the requirement of novel analyses or ground breaking conclusions.

- the **when, how and why** data was collected and what the data-product is.

Data journals and scientific publication of data

- The NERC data centres (and other repositories) can now cite datasets using DOIs
 - we can give academic credit to those scientists who get cited
- Publication – and scientific peer-review – is the next step
- We are working with the Royal Meteorological Society and Wiley-Blackwell to operate a new data journal, the Geoscience Data Journal
- GDJ is an online-only, Open Access journal, publishing short data papers cross-linked to – and citing – datasets that have been deposited in approved data centres and awarded DOIs.

Other data journals already exist – see a list (in no particular order) at:

<http://proj.badc.rl.ac.uk/preparde/blog/DataJournalsList>

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Introducing Scientific Data Updates
April 4, 2013

If not now then when – my view from within
April 3, 2013

[Press Release] NPG to launch Scientific Data to help scientists publish and reuse research data
April 3, 2013

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Scientific Data is a new open-access, online-only publication for descriptions of scientifically valuable datasets. It introduces a new type of content called the Data Descriptor, which will combine traditional narrative content with curated, structured descriptions of research data, including detailed methods and technical analyses supporting data quality.

PREPARDE: Peer REview for Publication & Accreditation of Research Data in the Earth sciences

Funded by JISC

Lead Institution: University of Leicester

Partners

- British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC)
- US National Centre for Atmospheric Research (NCAR)
- California Digital Library (CDL)
- Digital Curation Centre (DCC)
- University of Reading
- Wiley-Blackwell
- Faculty of 1000 Ltd

Project Lead: Dr Jonathan Tedds (University of Leicester, jat26@le.ac.uk)

Project Manager: Dr Sarah Callaghan (BADC, sarah.callaghan@stfc.ac.uk)

Length of Project: 12 months

Project Start Date: 1st July 2012

Project End Date: 31st June 2013

F1000Research

 because good research needs good data

PREPARDE topics

Example steps/workflow required for a researcher to publish a data paper

3 main areas of interest (in orange)

1. Workflows and cross-linking between journal and repository
 2. Repository accreditation
<http://bit.ly/ZhYHZI>
 3. Scientific peer-review of data
<http://bit.ly/DataPRforComment>
- Division of area of responsibilities between
 - *repository controlled* processes
 - *journal controlled* processes

The GBS dataset: measure x

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RMetS Geoscience Data Journal

Open Access

Data Paper

The GBS dataset: measurements of satellite site diversity at 20.7 GHz in the UK

S. A. Callaghan¹, J. Waight, J. L. Agnew, C. J. Walden, C. L. Wrench, S. Ventouras

Issue

Article first published online: 17 MAR 2013
DOI: 10.1002/gdj3.2

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The research presented in this paper was funded by the UK's Ofcom as part of the Spectrum Efficiency Scheme and the support of Ofcom in providing the funding for the GBS experiment is greatly appreciated.

Abstract Article References Cited By

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Keywords:
site diversity; radio propagation; fade mitigation techniques

Abstract

The GBS (Global Broadcast Service) dataset is a series of radio attenuation measurements made at three sites in the UK: Chilbolton and Sparsholt, both in southern UK, and Dundee in Scotland. The aim of the experiment was to make long term measurements of the signal strength received from a 20.7 GHz beacon on the US Department of Defense satellite UFO-9 at multiple sites, in order to determine whether the use of site diversity as a fade mitigation technique would be effective. The dataset spans a period of 3 years, from August 2003 to August 2006 with signal attenuation sampled once per second.

Dataset

The GBS (Global Broadcast Service) dataset comes as 3 separate data streams:

- Identifier: [doi:10.5285/639A3714-BC74-46A6-9026-64931F355E07](https://doi.org/10.5285/639A3714-BC74-46A6-9026-64931F355E07)
Creator: Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research, [Callaghan, S. A., J. Waight, C. J. Walden, J. Agnew and S. Ventouras].
Title: GBS 20.7 GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Chilbolton site
publisher: NERC British Atmospheric Data Centre
Publication year: 2009
Resource type: Metadata document
Version: 1.0
- Identifier: [doi:10.5285/db8d8981-1a51-4d6e-81c0-cced9b921390](https://doi.org/10.5285/db8d8981-1a51-4d6e-81c0-cced9b921390)
Creator: Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research, [Callaghan, S. A., J. Waight, C. J. Walden, J. Agnew and S. Ventouras].

Live Data Paper in Geoscience Data Journal!

Dataset citation is first thing in the paper (after abstract) and is also included in reference list (to take advantage of citation count systems)

DOI: 10.1002/gdj3.2

Viewing GBS 20.7GHz slant x

badc.nerc.ac.uk/view/badc.nerc.ac.uk_ATOM_dep_11902119479621181

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GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Chilbolton site

General Info

Title: GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Chilbolton site
Type: Activity
Sub-Type: Deployment
Publication State: Citable
URI: http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/view/badc.nerc.ac.uk_ATOM_dep_11902119479621181

Summary

The GBS (Global Broadcast Service) dataset is a series of radio attenuation measurements made at three sites in the UK: Chilbolton and Sparsholt, both in southern UK, and Dundee in Scotland. The aim of the experiment was to make long term measurements of the signal strength received from a 20.7GHz beacon on the US Department of Defense satellite UFO-9 at multiple sites, in order to determine whether the use of site diversity as a fade mitigation technique would be effective. The dataset spans a period of 3 years, from August 2003 to August 2006 with signal attenuation sampled once per second.

Please cite this dataset as:
 Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research, [S. A. Callaghan, J. Waight, C. J. Walden, J. Agnew and S. Ventouras], GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Sparsholt site, [Internet]. British Atmospheric Data Centre, 2003-2005. 1st April 2014. doi:10.1002/gdj3.2

This dataset is cited in:
 S. A. Callaghan, J. Waight, J.L.Agnew, C. J. Walden, C.L.Wrench, S. Ventouras "The GBS dataset: measurements of satellite site diversity at 20.7 GHz in the UK", Geoscience Data Journal, 17 March 2013, DOI: 10.1002/gdj3.2

Author

Name email
 Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research, [S. A. Callaghan, J. Waight, C. J. Walden, J. Agnew and S. Ventouras]

Online References

Relation	Title
Apply for access	Apply for to GBS data from Chilbolton
Download	Data directory for GBS data from Chilbolton
Documentation	DOI for dataset:10.5285/620-2714-1374-1636-2006-640216255e07
Documentation	Data article in Geoscience Data Journal doi:10.1002/gdj3.2

Associated Data

Type	Title
Data Production Tool	Chilbolton: GBS receiver
Activity	Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR)
Observation Station	Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR), UK

Dataset catalogue page (and DOI landing page) – again!

Reference to Data Article

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database abbreviation: data identifier

Data journals are a special case of journal publisher/data centre interactions.

There is still the need to link to data (held in repositories) from journal papers that mention/cite that data.

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Elsevier have updated their Guide for Authors text

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Elsevier working with NGDC to link through accession numbers

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Thanks to Bethan Keall (Elsevier)

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Abstract

Highlights

Keywords

- Introduction
- Materials and methods
 - Sampling
- Results and discussion
 - Grass samples
 - Other sample types including milk
- Conclusions

Addendum

Acknowledgements

References

Journal of Environmental Radioactivity

Volume 114, December 2012, Pages 48–53

Environmental Impacts of the Fukushima Accident (PART II)

Observations of Fukushima fallout in Great Britain

N.A. Beresford^a, C.L. Barnett^a, B.J. Howard^a, D.C. Howard^a, C. Wells^a, A.N. Tyler^b, S. Bradley^b, D. Copplestone^b

^a Centre for Ecology & Hydrology, Lancaster Environment Centre, Library Av., Bailrigg, Lancaster LA1 4AP, United Kingdom

^b Institute of Biological and Environmental Sciences, School of Natural Sciences, University of Stirling, Stirling FK9 4LA, United Kingdom

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2011.12.008>, How to Cite or Link Using DOI

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Abstract

Following the Fukushima accident in March 2011, grass samples were collected from 42 sites around Great Britain during April 2011. Iodine-131 was measurable in grass samples across the country with activity concentrations ranging from 10 to 55 Bq kg⁻¹ dry matter. Concentrations were similar to those reported in other European countries. Rainwater and some foodstuffs were also analysed from a limited number of sites. Of these, ¹³¹I was only detectable in sheep's milk (c. 2 Bq kg⁻¹). Caesium-134, which can be attributed to releases from the Fukushima reactors, was detectable in six of the grass samples (4–8 Bq kg⁻¹ dry matter); ¹³⁷Cs was detected in a larger number of grass samples although previous release sources (atmospheric weapons test and the 1986 Chernobyl and 1957 Windscale accidents) are likely to have contributed to this.

Highlights

► Grass samples from across Great Britain were sampled and analysed following releases from the Fukushima accident. ► Iodine-131 was detectable, at low levels, in grass samples from throughout the

Bibliographic information

N.A. Beresford, C.L. Barnett, B.J. Howard, D.C. Howard, C. Wells, A.N. Tyler, S. Bradley, D. Copplestone

Observations of Fukushima fallout in Great Britain

Journal of Environmental Radioactivity, Volume 114, December 2012, Pages 48–53
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2011.12.008>

Article history

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Abstract: Following the Fukushima accident in March 2011, grass samples were collected from 42 sites around Great Britain during April 2011. Iodine-131 was measurable in grass samples across the country with activity concentrations ranging from 10 to 55 Bq per kg dry matter. Concentrations were similar to those reported in other European countries. Rainwater and some foodstuffs were also analysed from a limited number of sites. Of these, I-131 was only detectable in sheep's milk (c. 2 Bq/kg). Caesium-134, which can be attributed to releases from the Fukushima reactors, was detectable in six of the grass samples (4-8 Bq/kg dry matter); 137Cs was detected in a larger number of grass samples although previous release sources (atmospheric weapons test and the 1986 Chernobyl and 1957 Windscale accidents) are likely to have contributed to this. All data and information for this sampling are available from this record. The data result from collaboration between CEH and the University of Stirling.

Resource Status: completed

Dataset Reference Date:

creation:	2011-08-03
publication:	2011-12-31

Other Citation Details: Beresford, N. A., Barnett, C. L., Howard, B. J., Howard, D. C., Tyler, A. N., Bradley, S., Copplestone, D. (2011) Observations of Fukushima Fallout in Great Britain. NERC- Environmental Information Data Centre doi:10.5285/1a91c7d1-ec44-4858-9af2-98d80f169bbd Link: http://dx.doi.org/10.5285/1a91c7d1-ec44-4858-9af2-98d80f169bbd

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What we've done and how we've done it

Data paper has been published in a data journal, linked via DOI to underlying dataset. Formal citations of datasets (also using DOIs) done in standard academic articles.

Can cite using URLs, but we've realised that people don't trust URLs. We're loading DOIs with more meaning than them simply being a persistent identifier – using them to signify completeness and technical quality of the dataset. We're also looking at citation counts as metric for dataset impact.

The day job – take in data and metadata supplied by scientists (often on a on-going basis). Make sure that there is adequate metadata and that the data files are appropriate format. Make it available to other interested parties.

Conclusions

- The NERC data centres now have the ability to mint DOIs and assign them to datasets in their archives. We have also produced:
 - guidelines for the data centre on what is an appropriate dataset to cite
 - guidelines for data providers about data citation and the sort of datasets we will cite
 - text in the NERC grants handbook telling grant applicants about data citation
- Other data centres/repositories/libraries are also minting DOIs for their data
- We're progressing well with data publication through our partnership with Wiley-Blackwell, and discussions with Elsevier and Thompson-Reuters. NERC held datasets have been published in data journals and cited in papers.
- Still plenty of work to do! Not just mechanical processes (e.g. workflows, guidelines) but also changing the culture so that citing and publishing data is the norm.

**KEEP
CALM
AND
CITE
DATA**

<http://www.keepcalm-omatic.co.uk/default.aspx#createposter>

Science not alchemy!

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data-publication@jiscmail.ac.uk

#preparde

Project website:

<http://proj.badc.rl.ac.uk/preparde/wiki>

Project blog:

<http://proj.badc.rl.ac.uk/preparde/blog>

Guidelines on peer review for data:

<http://bit.ly/DataPRforComment>

Guidelines for repository accreditation for
data publication: <http://bit.ly/ZhYHZI>

Feedback to:

<https://www.jiscmail.ac.uk/DATA-PUBLICATION>

Page from alchemic treatise of Ramon Llull
(Beginning of the 16th century)

http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Raimundus_Lullus_alchemic_page.jpg